

Errors of measurement in scientometrics: Identification and calculation of systematic errors

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Abstract

This paper focuses on systematic errors and propose how these can be measured and reported when informing and offering bibliometric data for policy purposes. We analysed differences in the calculation of impact indicators, when different 23 different classification schemes derived from Clarivate's InCites suite are used, specifically on five indicators: the Category Normalized Citation Indicator, the total number of citations, the H-index, the 1% of most cited articles, and the 10% of most cited articles. Findings show that citation counts are quite stable, with a difference of 13%. However, proportional indicators, such as top 1% and top 10% most cited articles, tend to vary more between universities, although on average they are lower than in the previous case. The results of this study can be used in estimating the error level in the research assessment of countries, institutions, and individuals.

Introduction

Errors are a natural and an unavoidable part of the scientific process. The measurement of a quantity can never be made with perfect accuracy, there will always be some error or uncertainty present (Scuro 2004). According to the Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology (2008), uncertainty is defined as a 'parameter associated with the result of a measurement, that characterizes the dispersion of the values that could reasonably be attributed to the measurand' (p. 2), being the measurand the object being measured. In the field of scientometrics, uncertainty and errors in measurement are usually overlooked. This is problematic for various reasons. First, by ignoring uncertainty, bibliometric indicators are used 'to legitimise decisions under conditions of lack of trust and/or political controversy' (Ràfols et al., 2016). Second, the sense of false precision fosters the use of league tables and rankings in which variations in positions may be the result of noise rather than improvement or decay, affecting the prestige of those being portrayed in such tables (Bastedo & Bowman, 2010). Moreover, almost all bibliometric indicators already show inherent shortcomings in their definition or calculation, which will even lead to the appearance of certain errors.

Next, we describe some of the most common types of bibliometric errors present in any study or bibliometric report.

- **False precision.** A prime example are the three decimals of the Journal Impact Factor. Garfield himself considered the impact factor accurate only up to one decimal place, and this fits in with his knowledge of the random error involved in classifying source items into "citable" and "non-citable" to construct the divisor of the measure (Bensman, 2007). He even admitted in later years that the only reason ISI calculated the impact factors reported in the JCRs out to three decimal places was to avoid the large number

of ties that would have resulted in listing many journals alphabetically in the impact factor rankings. The last statement is not only erroneous, but it would be inadmissible in any of the so-called exact sciences. Moreover, all analyses carried out under such a premise would de facto lose their validity, and we should not forget that this error has a profound effect particularly at the lower frequencies on ordinal rankings by the impact factor, on which most journal evaluations are based (Schloegl & Gorraiz, 2010).

- **Biases in data sources.** Another classic example is that of treating records retrieved from databases as populations rather than samples. There are many studies on the coverage of bibliometric data sources. In this respect, these studies point at the following biases or deficiencies of coverage of the most used databases (i.e., Web of Science and Scopus). These can be grouped into three biases: 1) language bias, favoring English literature over non-English (van Leeuwen et al., 2001); 2) disciplinary bias, being especially weak regarding their coverage for fields in the Social Sciences and Humanities (Hicks, 1999); and 3) mainstream biases, that is, coverage gaps with regard to locally relevant research (Rafols, Ciarli & Chavarro, 2015).
- **Inherent data errors.** The last common type of error has to do with incomplete or low-quality metadata (Franceschini, Maisano & Mastrogiacomo, 2015, 2016a; Selinova, Kosyakov & Guskov, 2019). These errors are like calibration errors in the experimental sciences. In the case of bibliometrics, we refer to the errors inherent in meta-data. Among them we can distinguish between errors derived from bad quality metadata, and those derived from processing errors. In the former category we would include issues such as the lack of a detailed classification of document types in some databases (Visser, van Eck, & Waltman, 2021). These errors may also be due to incompleteness of the bibliographic data. For example, from 1900 to 2015 over one-fifth of the publications indexed in WoS have completely missing information from the address field, which varies greatly among time periods, citation databases, document types, and publishing languages (Liu, Hu & Li 2018, Maddi). The latter category refers to issues such as the inclusion of the incorrect title in the cited reference list (Franceschini et al., 2016b) or errors, duplicates, and missing values regarding DOI (Gorraiz et al., 2016).

In general, two main types of errors in measurement are considered: systematic and random error. Systematic errors refer to those for which we know their cause. Random errors refer to those which are due to unknown causes. A third type of error could be those attributed to negligence, which in the case of scientometrics may occur when conducted by non-experts in what is commonly referred to as ‘desktop bibliometrics’ (Moed, 2020). In this research in progress, we focus on systematic errors and propose how these can be measured and reported when informing and offering bibliometric data for policy purposes. We want to exemplify systematic errors through the problems involved in the use of different classification schemes. In this first attempt we will focus on differences in the calculation of citation impact indicators when using different classification scheme specially at institutional level. Differences are due to the classification scheme used and how publications are categorized differently according to the scheme. Also, they can be due to the inclusion or exclusion of some of the records due to their unfitness regarding the classification scheme (e.g., the Essential Science Indicators classification scheme does not consider the fields of Arts and Humanities). Specifically, we will focus on five indicators and 23 classification schemes and its effects over 8000 institutions.

Table 1. Description of the 23 classification schemes employed for the analysis*

Denomination	Description	Levels and Categories	Method
ANVUR Category Schema	Official academic fields and disciplines list for Italian Universities Research and Teaching.	(1) 17 broad categories	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
Australia ERA FOR	Revised Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification (ANZSRC 2020)	(1) 24 FoR2 (2) 24 FoR4	Journal mapping
CAPEs Brazil	Classification created by the Foundation CAPEs, linked to the Ministry of Education (Brazil)	(1) Capes 9 (2) Capes 49 (3) Capes 121	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
China SCADC Subject Categories	State Council Academic Degree Committee (SCADC) and Ministry of Education of China	(1) Broader 13 (2) Granular 96	Journal and other sources mapping
Shanghai Ranking Global Ranking of Subjects	Rankings of universities in 54 subjects across, Natural, , Life, Medical, and Social Sciences...	(1) 54 academic subjects	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
Citation Topics	Algorithmically derived citation clusters (using an algorithm developed by CWTS, Leiden)	(1) Macro 10 (2) Meso 326	algorithmically on citation relationships
Essential Science Indicators Research Areas	All documents from Science Citation Index Expanded and Social Science Citation Index	(1) 22 broad categories	Journal mapping
FAPESP Brazil	Created by the São Paulo Research Foundation	(1) 9 High Level (2) 72 Detailed categories	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
Institutional Profiles Research Areas	Clarivate Analytics has been profiling the world's leading universities and research institutions	(1) 6 broad academic fields	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
KAKEN Category Schema (10 and 66)	From Japan called the Kakenhi Program (Grants-in-Aid for Scientific Research).	(1) 10 L2 (2) 66 L3	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
OECD Category Schema	Revised Field of Science and Technology (FOS) Classification of the Frascati Manual.	(1) 6 Major (2) 42 Minor	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
PL19 Category Schema	The Polish PL19 category schema is used for annual evaluation exercise	(1) 44 underlying categories	Journal mapping
Research and Innovation Strategies for Specialization	The Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialization (RIS3) for Latvia	(1) 7 specialization fields	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
UK RAE Units of Assessment 2008	UK 2008 Research Assessment Exercise (RAE) Units of Assessment (UoA)	(1) 67 categories	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
UK REF Units of Assessment 2014	UK 2014 Research Assessment Exercise (RAE) Units of Assessment (UoA)	(1) 36 units of assessment	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
Web of Science Research Areas	The Web of Science schema comprises approximately 250 subject areas	(1) 250	---

* Information extracted from <https://incites.help.clarivate.com/Content/Research-Areas/research-areas.htm>

Data and methods

Data collection

Data was retrieved using the bibliometric suite *InCites*, which includes the Web of Science Core Collection including the *Emerging Sources Citation Index* (ESCI), for the period 1980-2022. In this study we worked at the institutional level, using their “Organizations” option, that is, their disambiguated list of institutions (more on issues for disambiguating institutional names in Waltman et al., 2012). We only worked with institutions which had at least 1,000 publications in the study period. Our final dataset includes 8,079 institutions. We retrieved for each institution their total number of publications and five citation impact indicators: the Category Normalized Citation Indicator, total number of citations, H-Index, top 1% most cited papers, and top 10% most cited papers. Each indicator is computed 23 times according to each different classification schemes offered by InCites. Table 1 includes the list of schemes as well as a brief description of each of them. This table included very well-known classifications as Web of Science or ESI. We have also indicated the method we have also indicated, mainly Category-to-category mapping (WoS) and Journal mapping

Calculation of errors

The calculation of the errors followed the standard definition used in the experimental sciences, where the absolute error of a measurement is the difference between the measured value and the true value. As the latter is usually absent, this value is replaced with the mean value after iterating the measurement. In our case, each indicator is calculated a total of 23 times. Based on the individual absolute errors of each institution, we can compute the arithmetic mean of all absolute errors. Which is defined as follows:

$$\Delta x_{\text{mean}} = (\text{ABS}(\Delta x_1) + \text{ABS}(\Delta x_1) + \dots + \text{ABS}(\Delta x_n))/n$$

Where x_i corresponds to an institution and $\text{ABS}(\Delta x_i)$ is its absolute error.

Based on the absolute error it is possible to compute relative and percentage errors which allow comparisons between indicators.

Results

Following we include some preliminary results of our first analyses. Figure 1 includes top 25 most productive institutions according to Web of Science, their mean CNCI according to the 23 different classification schemes used and their absolute error. As observed, Harvard University is the institution with the highest impact (2.24), followed by Harvard Medical School (2.17) and the NIH (2.01). But acknowledging the existence of an error in measurement, means that its real position ranges somewhere between the first and third positions. Furthermore, 15 of the top institutions could actually position themselves within the top 10 positions given the uncertainty surrounding the measurement. In this way we can create blocks of positions as we cannot point clearly at actual positions given the uncertainty of our measurement.

Figure 1. Error bars of the Category Normalized Citation Impact (CNCI) of the top 25 most productive institutions according to InCites in the 2017-2021 period

Interestingly, we observe that the stability of errors varies by indicator. In Figure 2 and we observe the distribution of relative errors in the measurement of five citation indicators. Errors on citation counts are quite stable, being off by 13%. However, proportional indicators such as the share of top 1% most cited papers or top 10% most cited papers tend to vary more across universities, although on average they are smaller than in former case.

Figure 2. Distribution of the relative error for five citation indicators.

Finally, we compute in table 2 the global errors per indicator based on the 23 classification schemes analysed. The results show that the mean percentage error varies from 4.5% to 17.4% and that the most affected indicator is the percentage of the Top 1% most cited documents. This seems reasonable given that we are dealing with a low number of publications which making it up to such citation threshold.

Table 2. Global errors due to the use of different classifications or levels of classification

	Total Percentage Error	
	Mean Percentage Error	Absolute Error +/-
Times Cited	9.37	0.81
CNCI	6.64	3.02
% Documents in Top 1%	17.42	8.96
% Documents in Top 10%	7.96	3.09
H-Index	4.47	0.68

Conclusions

This paper presents a first attempt at accounting for uncertainty and errors in measurement in bibliometric studies. Although acknowledge in the literature, these errors are rarely reported in bibliometric reports, misleading users and leading to malpractices on the use of bibliometric indicators. The spread of bibliometric indicators in research evaluation and policy has been accompanied by an increasing realisation that indicators' use is often problematic and/or inappropriate. Any use of indicators for evaluation purposes implies acceptance of a set of assumptions and criteria. First and foremost, we need to assume that the indicators reflect adequately the properties and context that are important for policy, with the overall research objective (Molas & Rafols, 2018) to avoid the "evaluation gap" "between evaluation criteria and the social and economic functions of science" (Wouters, 2014). In this paper we highlight error size on the measurement of citation indicators by using different classification schemes at the meso-level. To understand the relation between these levels of classification and research evaluation and classification practices, scientific publications need to be considered as boundary objects within research evaluation infrastructures. Considering different levels of evaluation processes, different levels of evaluation, and the different research fields is important to responsibly monitor and report performance using quantitative indicators. We expect to continue expanding this work by calculating errors of measurement at different units of analyses (e.g., researchers, countries) and looking into other sources of systematic error (e.g., differences on coverage between databases, quality of metadata, definition of document types).

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